
Comparison between the actual Federal Funds Rate and the Interest Rate suggested by the Taylor Rule

A Data Management Plan created using dmponline

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Project abstract:

With this data experiment we want to show that the federal funds rate called by the FED has a very strong correlation with the Taylor rule. A determination of this correlation is desirable because the Taylor rule is commonly used to forecast FED monetary policy. The Taylor rule which was invented and published 1992 by John Taylor is a forecasting model that determines what interest rate should be to shift the economy toward stable prices and full employment.

Last modified: 15-04-2021

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Data description and collection or re-use of existing data

How will new data be collected or produced and/or how will existing data be re-used?

Data collected:

The project uses data which is downloaded from the website of the Federal Reserve Economic Data (<https://fred.stlouisfed.org/>) which is a database maintained by the Research division of the Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis

- Effective Federal Funds Rate: The csv file was downloaded from Board of Governors of the Federal Reserve System (US), Effective Federal Funds Rate [FEDFUNDS], retrieved from FRED, Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis; <https://fred.stlouisfed.org/series/FEDFUNDS>, März 22, 2021 with the parameters: annual, 1977-2017
- Output Gap: The csv file was downloaded from U.S. Bureau of Economic Analysis, Real Gross Domestic Product [GDPC1], retrieved from FRED, Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis; <https://fred.stlouisfed.org/series/GDPC1>, März 22, 2021. with the parameters: annual, 1977-2017
- Inflation (regarding consumer prices): The csv file was downloaded from World Bank, Inflation, consumer prices for the United States [FPCPITOTLZGUSA], retrieved from FRED, Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis; <https://fred.stlouisfed.org/series/FPCPITOTLZGUSA>, März 22, 2021. with the parameters: 1977-2017

In addition to that the collected data can be accessed via my

Data/Files produced:

I am producing the code using R (version 3.6.3) with RStudio (with only the base packages).

The output csv and jpeg file will be created by executing this code.

The code can be accessed via my public github repository:

<https://github.com/floom9/Comparison-between-the-actual-Federal-Funds-Rate-and-the-Taylor-Rule>

What data (for example the kinds, formats, and volumes) will be collected or produced?

Data collected:

3 csv files:

- Effective Federal Funds Rate (name: FEDFUNDS.csv)

- location: <https://github.com/floom9/Comparison-between-the-actual-Federal-Funds-Rate-and-the-Taylor-Rule/tree/main/Data>
- size: 1.25kb
- Inflation (name: inflation.csv)
 - location: <https://github.com/floom9/Comparison-between-the-actual-Federal-Funds-Rate-and-the-Taylor-Rule/tree/main/Data>
 - size: 1.14kb
- Output gap (name: output_gap.csv)
 - location: <https://github.com/floom9/Comparison-between-the-actual-Federal-Funds-Rate-and-the-Taylor-Rule/tree/main/Data>
 - size: 1.32kb

Data produced:

- csv file
 - name: taylor.csv
 - DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4678242>
 - location: <https://github.com/floom9/Comparison-between-the-actual-Federal-Funds-Rate-and-the-Taylor-Rule/tree/main/Results>
 - size: 1.13kb

Files produced:

- code
 - name: Source Code.R
 - location: <https://github.com/floom9/Comparison-between-the-actual-Federal-Funds-Rate-and-the-Taylor-Rule>
 - size: 812bytes
- Plot
 - name: comparison_plot.jpeg
 - DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4678409>
 - location: <https://github.com/floom9/Comparison-between-the-actual-Federal-Funds-Rate-and-the-Taylor-Rule/tree/main/Results>
 - size: 22.4kb

Documentation and data quality

What metadata and documentation (for example the methodology of data collection and way of organising data) will accompany data?

Md files containing the metadata can be found here:

<https://github.com/floom9/Comparison-between-the-actual-Federal-Funds-Rate-and-the-Taylor-Rule/tree/main/Metadata>

The README.md file contains a guide on how to reproduce the experiment.

It can be found on my public accessible github repository:

<https://github.com/floom9/Comparison-between-the-actual-Federal-Funds-Rate-and-the-Taylor-Rule>

What data quality control measures will be used?

Data quality checks like consistency of labels, logical errors, etc. will be done.

Storage and backup during the research process

How will data and metadata be stored and backed up during the research process?

The collected data and produced data/files are stored locally and on my github repository <https://github.com/floom9/Comparison-between-the-actual-Federal-Funds-Rate-and-the-Taylor-Rule> during the experiment.

How will data security and protection of sensitive data be taken care of during the research?

Since no sensitive data is used, this is not necessary.

Legal and ethical requirements, codes of conduct

If personal data are processed, how will compliance with legislation on personal data and on data security be ensured?

Since no personal data is used, this is not necessary.

How will other legal issues, such as intellectual property rights and ownership, be managed? What legislation is applicable?

Data collected:

Inflation:

Intellectual property of The World Bank <https://www.worldbank.org/en/home>

The data is under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International licence

Federal Funds rate:

Intellectual property of the Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis

The corresponding terms of use and licenses can be seen here:

<https://fred.stlouisfed.org/legal/#full-fred-terms>

The Freedom of Information act (FOIA) applies here

Output Gap:

Intellectual property of the U.S. Bureau of Economic Analysis (<https://www.bea.gov>)

Information about the data policies is provided here:

<https://www.bea.gov/about/policies-and-information>

The Freedom of Information act (FOIA) applies here

Data/Files produced:

Owned by: Florian Mayer

The csv/jpeg files produced will be licenced under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International licence

The code will be licensed under the MIT license.

How will possible ethical issues be taken into account, and codes of conduct followed?

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project.

Data sharing and long-term preservation

How and when will data be shared? Are there possible restrictions to data sharing or embargo reasons?

After the experiment the code will be publically available on github:

<https://github.com/floom9/Comparison-between-the-actual-Federal-Funds-Rate-and-the-Taylor-Rule>

In addition to that the csv and jpeg files will be stored on Zenodo:

taylor.csv:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4678242>

comparison_plot.jpeg:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4678409>

There are no restriction to data sharing or embargo reasons.

How will data for preservation be selected, and where will data be preserved long-term (for example a data repository or archive)?

For long-term archiving of and access to the datasets, the Zenodo repository will be used. For source code, GitHub will be used.

What methods or software tools will be needed to access and use the data?

R (version 3.6.3) will be needed to execute the source code.

How will the application of a unique and persistent identifier (such as a Digital Object Identifier (DOI)) to each data set be ensured?

A DOI will be assigned (using Zenodo and GitHub integration).

Data management responsibilities and resources

Who (for example role, position, and institution) will be responsible for data management (i.e. the data steward)?

Florian Mayer is the only person working on this experiment and therefore also responsible for data management

What resources (for example financial and time) will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable)?

No additional resources are needed for data management and storage.